

Book Reviews

Julie Dolan, Melissa M. Deckman, Michele L. Swers, *Women and Politics: Paths to Power and Political Influence* (4th ed.), Rowman & Littlefield, 2021, Pages: 448.

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Women and Politics: Paths to Power and Political Influence (4th ed.) entails the stories of women as political movers and policymakers at various levels of government, such as federal, state, city, and local governments, along with the judiciary. The book explores latest research in the political sphere while focusing on historical events and critical aspects of the women's movement. It also profiles various women and their perspectives and experiences in politics. The book is divided into two parts. Part I talks about the trajectory women followed to acquire power in the political realm. Part II focuses on women in power at the different levels of the political system, namely: Legislature, Executive, Judiciary, and local level governance.

Part I, Chapter 2: "Women's Paths to Power" dives deeper into the major social movements that altered the course of women's rights. This chapter examines how modern women's organizations compete to shape political debates and offer solutions to the policies that reflect "what women truly want." The initial pages talk about the seven decades of women's movement to win the right to vote in the United States. Associations like the National Woman Suffrage Association (NWSA), American Woman Suffrage Association (AWSA), General Federation of Women's Clubs (GFWC), and Women's Christian Temperance Union (WCTU) dedicated their fight to win an amendment for women's suffrage. This chapter covers the "second wave" of feminism that emerged a few decades after women gained their right to vote, where men and women both adjusted to societal transitions in women's roles. As from 1960s onwards, more and more women started contributing to household income,

The book unfolds how the second wave focused more on public and private injustice against women. Rape, reproductive rights, domestic violence, and workplace safety were the major

issues highlighted in this movement. It entails how women have teamed up together to fight discrimination at the workplace, in the state, in the society and also in the federal law. The book dives deep into these battles and how they resulted in the failed attempt to add an “Equal Rights Amendment “(ERA) in the US Constitution. The Equal Rights Amendment was an amendment proposed to the United States Constitution that would provide equal legal rights to all American citizens without discriminating them on the basis of their gender.

The Gender Gap in Elections and Public Opinion investigates gender differences in voting behaviour and the political attitudes of the masses. The gender gap is an important issue in the contemporary US electoral politics along with the challenges of African Americans, Latinos, and Asian Americans. The chapter also examines the origins of the gender gap in voting and widely discusses the gender gap in American politics. With the help of various graphs and numerical data, the authors back the study of gender gap in American politics. In final pages the authors investigate whether women voters are key supporters of women candidates or not while studying Hillary Clinton's Presidential campaigns in 2016 and her support amongst the male and female voters.

Gender and the Decision to Run for Office, examines how women are underestimated in their decision to run for the office and how they are less likely to be selected as a candidate to run for elections or even in the political parties. It focuses on Ashley Bennett, an African American healthcare worker's election campaign for the local county, in 2017. This issue highlights why female candidates are more likely to take their decision as a desire to help their communities and address policy issues that are particularly important to their districts. The author touches on the fact that family obligations will continue to corner some women; their deep relationships and commitments to family members can also serve as powerful factors.

Women on the Campaign Trail, the author discusses how women persuade voters that they belong in the masculine world of politics and why female candidates must navigate gender and empower themselves in politics. It focuses on the historic Presidential campaign of Kamala Harris in 2019. Chapter I highlights the drawbacks and challenges faced by Harris and other women candidates during their election campaigns in addition to what factors made them withdraw from the same. The author provides detailed view on how voters perceive female candidates and how different they are from their male counterparts. Men have certain masculine traits, and female candidates are perceived to be more empathetic, moral, genuine,

and ethical than their male counterparts. There is a parallel drawn by voters as men are tough, better capable of handling emergencies, and more capable than women. Voters believe men are good at dealing with the economy, taxes, the military, and crime that women are more capable of dealing with health care, social security, and education issues.

In the section on *Women in Local Politics and Government*, the author discusses how women are making an impact as elected officials and activists in non-governmental and grassroots organizations. It highlights how gender differences in local politics may be related to the expectations and constraints of local governance whereas at the national and state tiers, women tend to be Democrats with much more liberal views than men. Having said that by the end of the book, the author gives a view that same cannot be said about women in local politics. *Women in Congress and the State Legislatures*, focuses on the history of women's inclusion in the United States Congress and the fifty state legislative bodies. It investigates the commonalities and differences in male and female legislators' policy activities and leadership styles. The authors bring out the elements of the political environment that influence female legislators' ability and willingness to work for policy changes on behalf of various groups of women. The book also focuses on the 2018 elections, which had the most ethnically and racially diverse class of women in the House of Representatives, along with the advancement of women in Congress since the 1920s.

"Women in the Executive Branch" examines women's contributions to governance within the executive branch of government. The book holds a descriptive representation of women as Governors, Presidential Cabinet members, etc. It highlights the barriers and challenges to the substantive representation of women at the Executive level in the government. Overall, the author talks about how women have made great strides in their overall representation in executive branch positions throughout the American government. In the section on *Women in the Judiciary*, the author investigates the number of women serving as judges in the United States and the history of women in the courts. It also examines the legal system in American politics, focusing on how gender may affect this branch of government. It focuses on what differences female judges make in the political system. Politically progressive women frequently advocate for the state to play a larger role in providing social welfare programs for women and their families.

The authors conclude the book by highlighting how strong women can be found in every walk of life. They did not begin their careers in politics but rather as women who believed they could bring change and better their communities if they became more involved. The authors believe that due to women's participation, the economy and stance of the United States has flourished globally.